

Event Abstract

Knowledge, Attitude and Practice Regarding Life Style Modification in Type 2 Diabetic Patients in Alakwash Polyclinic, Tripoli During 2016

Yousef Sharfaddin ^{1*}

¹ Alakwash polyclinic, Tripoli, Libya.

² Airport Road polyclinic, Tripoli, Libya.

Background: The number of persons suffering from type 2 diabetes mellitus continues to rise worldwide and causes significant morbidity and mortality, especially in the developing world. Behaviour change and adoption of healthy lifestyle habits help to prevent or slow down the complications of type 2 diabetes mellitus. This study aimed at studying the knowledge, attitude and practices regarding lifestyle modification among type II diabetic patients attending the out patients Alakwash polyclinic, Tripoli.

Methods: A cross-sectional study using a structured questioner included 228 diabetic patients attending Alakwash-outpatients diabetic clinic in Tripoli.

Results: The age ranged between 30 years to 90 years with mean 56.7±11.6years, Female to male ratio was 1.6:1, female constitute to 61.8% of the patients. Majority of patients were married (85%). Illiterate constitute to 22.8% of the patients, more than half of them had secondary school or higher graduation (61.8%). Nearly half of the patients were unemployed (46.5%). Duration of diabetes was ≤5 years in 40.4% and >5years in 59.6%. Treatment with insulin was recorded in 29.8%. Complication of diabetes was recorded in 59.2% of the patients. Majority of patients had knowledge about diabetes (97.8%). Source of knowledge obtained from medical staff in (71.5%), from television. Majority of patients had knowledge about what is diabetes, (96.5%) know that diabetes means high blood sugar. About symptoms of diabetes the patients gave correct answer in (87.7%) for the increase in weight as symptom of diabetes and 3.1% about frequency of urination as symptom of diabetes

and (3.5%). Known that the thirst a symptom of diabetes Knowledge of patients about symptoms of hypoglycemia; (86.8%) knows the correct answer about that sense of hunger a symptom of hypoglycemia. Knowledge about foot care; answers was correct in (80.7%) about walking barefoot risk factor of diabetes, (77.6%) correct answer about treatment of any fungus between the toes and cuts of the ways, (83%) correct answer about Protect the feet from injury of the ways of attention to diabetic patient and (81%) correct answer about use of un- flexible shoes protect the diabetic feet. Knowledge of patients about prevention of diabetes ;(96%) correct answer about the exercise regularly prevent diabetes, (87.7%) correct answer about (86%) and (92.5%) correct answer about healthy diet prevent diabetes. Knowledge about effect of regular exercise on diabetes; correct answer was (95.2%) for regular exercise control weight;(91.2%) correct answer for regular exercise reduce blood sugar, (66.7%) correct answer regular exercise increase fat and (76.8%) correct answer for regular exercise reduce stress. Knowledge of patients about diabetic diet, (91.2%) correct answer for high amount of carbohydrates, (91.2%) correct answer for a small amount of vegetables, (79%) correct answer for high amount of fruit, (93%) correct answer for low amount of sugar and (82.5%) correct answer for high amount of fat. Attitude of patients about diabetes; (69.3%) correct answer for diabetic patients when take insulin treatment can eat without restriction, (68%) correct answer for diabetic patients when use insulin

treatment indicated the person has reached last stage of disease. Practices sport regularly recorded in (53.5%). Regular analysis of blood sugar done by (60.5%). Examination of eye done by (39%) of patients, urine examination done by (44.7%), changing the site of insulin injection done by (79%), storage the insulin in right way done by (87.3%) and (97.4%) can adjust the insulin dose.

Conclusion: It was observed that majority of the patients in the study had adequate knowledge, good attitude and fair practice regarding diabetes control.

Keywords: Primary Care, Libya, diabetes mellitus, Behaviour change and healthy lifestyle.

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* **Correspondence:** Dr Yousef Sharfaddin, Alakwash polyclinic, Tripoli, Libya, dr.yes2012@gmail.com